

**ЛЕЙОМІОМА МАТКИ, ЯК ФАКТОР РИЗИКУ ВИНИКНЕННЯ
ГЕНІТАЛЬНИХ ПРОЛАПСІВ
UTERINE LEIOMYOMA AS A RISK FACTOR OF GENITAL
PROLAPSE**

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Introduction. In today's world, much attention is paid to the quality of life, unfortunately, genital prolapse (GP) significantly affects all areas of women's lives. According to the WHO, the incidence of GP by 2030 may reach 63 million. This disease is multifactorial, the main and most studied of them: reproductive history, age, dysplastic connective tissue diseases, increased intra-abdominal pressure, overweight, and smoking. There are a large number of different operations for the correction of GP, it should be noted that the frequency of their implementation varies from 6 to 18%. The role of concomitant genital pathology in modern literature is almost unexplored.

Goal. Study of the role of concomitant genital pathology, namely uterine leiomyoma in the occurrence of GP in order to increase the role of prevention effectiveness in progression and timely surgical treatment of women with GP.

Materials and methods. A retrospective analysis of 300 case histories of inpatients with GP was performed.

Results of the research. After processing obtained data, concomitant genital pathology was detected in 55% of patients. It was found that GP was combined with: uterine leiomyoma in 30% of patients, endometrial hyperplasia - in 5%, ovarian cysts in 10% and adenomyosis in 10% of patients. It is noteworthy that in 25% of patients leiomyoma was an indication for uterine extirpation, and in 5% of cases, uterine amputation was performed.

Conclusions. Uterine leiomyoma occupies an important place among the concomitant genital pathology in pelvic prolapse, it is necessary to assess its more detailed role of it as a risk factor for GP. It is also necessary to develop an algorithm for selecting the volume of the operation to minimize further progression of GP.